

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Impact of crop diversification and the use of trap plants on the profitability of potato production in Galicia

Assessing the profitability of different cropping strategies is essential to understand their economic viability and long-term sustainability. This study analyses the impact on the profitability of three approaches: (T1) conventional cropping (potato / wheat / potato), (T2) rotation with legumes (wheat / peas / potato) and (T3) trap crops (potato / vetch + oats + trap crop / potato), providing a clear view of the financial impact of each practice at the farm level.

To compare the three experiments, only the yields of a two-year cycle are analysed. i.e. 1 rotation (alternative crop plus potato). As the graphs show, the rotation with legumes is the most profitable in terms of productivity and financial stability (less variability), thanks to a significant reduction in production costs and very important increases in gross margin of 107% and

126% compared to the conventional and trap crop strategies, respectively (3,350 €/ha extra compared to conventional).

The results of the success of the legume treatment can be influenced by the previous crop rotation (wheat instead of potatoes), which could have a positive effect on the yield of the subsequent crop. This strategy improves economic resilience and reduces dependence on external external inputs.

This economic-financial analysis is the key to helping farmers to make informed decisions, optimise income, and minimise risk in a context of price volatility and increasing pressure for agricultural sustainability. And also, for the design of agricultural policies.

1. Graph showing how the gross margins variability according to the different agricultural practices applied in a two-year cycle. It shows the general distribution of the data obtained, including the most common values (shaded box), the average (black line) and the extremes (highest and lowest).

	Direct costs (€/ha)	Sales revenue (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Conventional	10,535	12,205	3,134
T2: Legume	8,593	13,462	6,484
T3: Trap crop	8,938	10,541	2,867

2. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 2-year rotation (alternative crop - potato).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, legumes, trap crop, crop diversification

AUTHORSHIP

Miguel Rodríguez Méndez, GEN research group, ECOBAS, Universidade de Vigo
Marina Gómez Rodríguez, GEN research group, ECOBAS, Universidade de Vigo

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

This factsheet is produced as part of the SoildiverAgro project. Although the author has worked on the best information available, neither the author nor the EU shall in any event be liable for any loss, damage or injury incurred directly or indirectly in relation to the project.